

THE METHOD OF DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN THE FORMATION OF COGNITIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: The article examines the importance of developing critical thinking in younger schoolchildren in the context of the modern educational environment, where the emphasis is on creativity and cognitive culture. The authors emphasize that critical thinking contributes to the formation of cognitive competence and important skills necessary for successful learning and personal development. The article presents the main aspects of critical thinking and methods of its development in younger schoolchildren, such as role-playing games, educational simulations, discussions, correct formulation of questions and research projects. The authors believe that these methods contribute to the effective formation of cognitive competence in children based on critical thinking.

Keywords: critical thinking, education, cognitive competence, learning process, teaching methods, analytical skills, synthetic skills, problem thinking, discussions, role-playing games, research projects, assessment skills, critical perception of information, independence.

Currently, students face difficulties in gaining knowledge and finding information due to difficulties in understanding educational material due to lack of sufficient interest and motivation. This is due to the insufficient development of critical thinking in children. But critical thinking is very important in today's world, where a cognitive culture prevails that values creativity rather than just a traditional approach to knowledge.

Instead of simply memorizing information, students are encouraged to focus and creatively use their knowledge to find problems [1].

Critical thinking is the ability of a person to objectively evaluate himself and other people's ideas, carefully check all proposed thoughts and conclusions. Creative or critical thinking helps a person to determine their priorities in personal and professional life, assumes personal responsibility for choice, increases the level of individual culture of working with information, forms the ability to analyze and draw independent conclusions, predict the results of their decisions and take responsibility for them, allows you to develop a culture of communication in joint activities [2].

The mechanism of critical thinking consists of thought processes that form reasoning. They include setting a goal, defining a problem, formulating hypotheses (assumptions), presenting evidence, justifying them, predicting results, and accepting or rejecting alternative points of view. Critical thinking also refers to the ability to use basic intellectual skills to analyze, synthesize, and evaluate complex, controversial situations and issues. This includes skills in identifying problems, analyzing facts, in-depth study of the problem, creating criteria for evaluating solutions, as well as evaluating the reliability of information sources and avoiding generalizations.

Currently, there are many definitions of critical thinking in the pedagogical literature. For example, D.V. Halpern in his work "Psychology of critical Thinking" describes it as the use

of cognitive methods and approaches that increase the likelihood of achieving the desired result [3].

This definition describes critical thinking as a characteristic characterized by control, justification, and expediency. This type of thinking is used in solving various problems, making informed conclusions, probabilistic assessment and making effective decisions. The student uses skills that are reasonable and effective for the specific situation and the type of problem being solved. Critical thinking also involves evaluating the factors that the thought process takes into account when making decisions.

D.Kluster In the article «What is critical thinking» highlights the following aspects of critical thinking:

1. Critical thinking is independent thinking;
2. Information is not the starting point, but the end point of critical thinking.
3. Critical thinking begins with asking questions and identifying the problems that need to be solved.;
4. Critical thinking strives for convincing evidence;
5. Critical thinking is considered social thinking [4].

Critical thinking is a complex process that involves the skills of thinking about one's own mental activity. This includes working with certain concepts, reasoning, and conclusions. It is also important to develop analytical skills and evaluate the analogical capabilities of people around you. The practical orientation of critical thinking allows us to interpret it as a form of practical logic, depending on the context of thinking and the individual characteristics of the subject. [5].

We believe that the development of critical thinking plays an important role in the formation of cognitive competence of younger schoolchildren, as it contributes to the development of a number of important skills and abilities necessary for a successful learning process and personal development.

Here are some of the ways in which the development of critical thinking can affect the formation of cognitive competencies of younger students:

Analytical skills: Critical thinking helps students understand information, analyze it, highlight key aspects and key ideas. This is an important skill that allows them to understand texts, tasks and problems;

Synthetic skills: *Synthetic skills:* The ability to combine different ideas, concepts and facts into a single whole is also an important aspect of critical thinking. Developing this skill allows students to generate new knowledge and understanding based on available information;

Ability to evaluate: Critical thinking helps students evaluate data, ideas, and evidence according to their validity, adequacy, and significance. This skill allows them to make informed decisions and formulate their point of view;

Ability to evaluate: Critical thinking helps students evaluate data, ideas, and evidence based on their validity, adequacy, and relevance. This skill allows them to make the right decisions and formulate their point of view;

Problem thinking: The development of critical thinking helps students develop problem-solving skills, as it teaches them to look for alternative ways and strategies to achieve a goal, as well as analyze the possible consequences of their actions;

Critical perception of information: Primary school students often encounter different information from different sources. The development of critical thinking helps them to critically perceive this information, to separate facts from opinions;

Independence and Initiative: Critical thinking helps students develop independent thinking and decision-making skills. This allows them to take the initiative in the learning process and in everyday life.

Thus, the development of critical thinking plays an important role in the formation of cognitive competence of younger schoolchildren, helps them develop analytical, synthetic, evaluative skills, as well as skills of problem thinking, critical perception of information and independence.

1. Role-playing games and educational simulations:

Role-playing games and learning simulations help students understand complex concepts and problems more comfortably. It also helps them develop critical thinking, as they need to know how to make decisions within their role.

2. Munozaralar orqali tanqidiy fikrlashni rag'batlantirish:

Organizing discussions on various topics helps students learn how to discuss their point of view, analyze opponents' arguments and draw conclusions.

3. We teach you how to ask questions correctly:

It is important to teach elementary school students how to ask questions correctly so that they can critically examine information.

4. Research projects:

Students can work on research projects to explore a specific topic and develop critical thinking. They must identify the problem, collect and analyze the data, draw conclusions and present the results.

These methods can give a positive result in the formation of cognitive competence in younger schoolchildren based on critical thinking.

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